

standICT.eu 2026
ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation

With a focus on the Republic of Korea

Post-event Report

ONLINE EVENT

15th April 2025

09:00 - 10:30 CEST | 🇰🇷 16:00-17:30 KST

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The StandICT.eu Standards Training Academy, in collaboration with INSTAR, hosted a webinar on 15 April 2025 (9:00–10:30 CEST / 16:00–17:30 KST) focused on the Republic of Korea's strategies and activities in ICT standardisation.

For decades, the Republic of Korea has positioned itself as a strong and recognised actor in international standardisation, particularly in the ICT domain. This is reflected not only in the volume of patent applications by its major multinationals but also in their declared standard-essential patents.

The webinar offered an overview of the Republic of Korea's current standardisation landscape and strategic direction, with a particular emphasis on the ICT sector.

The first part explored the opportunities and challenges encountered by Korean stakeholders in international standardisation, including the impact of ongoing geopolitical dynamics.

The discussion then shifted to the implications for the EU, highlighting opportunities for increased collaboration, joint initiatives, and shared responses to global challenges.

TAKEAWAYS

⌵ Despite rising digital tensions, ICT standards offer a path to address global challenges like climate change. This makes international cooperation on standards more important than ever.

⌵ TTA focuses on Korean domestic needs but acknowledges the value of global regulation.

Engagement with EU efforts like the Cyber Resilience Act shows growing openness to international alignment and harmonisation.

⌵ Standard setting is now a key instrument of global influence, especially in AI and 5G.

Countries increasingly integrate standardisation into their national strategy, industry policy, and international diplomacy.

⌵ The Republic of Korea aims to export domestic standards in areas like green tech and cybersecurity. Efforts target both developing and developed regions, pushing for international relevance across global markets.

⌵ The Republic of Korea plays a key role in global standardisation, balancing challenges and opportunities. Collaboration with international bodies and the EU is vital to shape and influence global standards.

EXPERTS QUOTES

Knut Blind:

The main goal is to strengthen the role of European experts in international standardisation. This is supported through funding, observatories, working groups, and strategic forums. This webinar fits into this framework by informing and training the next generation of ICT standardisation professionals, ensuring continued European engagement and expertise.

Kihun KIM:

In a world marked by growing tech power struggles, no single country should shape the global tech system alone. Europe and the Republic of Korea can jointly promote a more balanced, inclusive, and socially responsible data system through standardisation. Our collaboration with the EU is not just about writing technical documents; it is about shaping how technology affects our society.

Kyoung Seok Oh:

TTA follows three strategic pillars: advancing standards in emerging tech like 6G and quantum, digitising the standardisation process, and expanding international cooperation. A detailed strategy map helps align national priorities with global SDOs, with INSTAR collaboration supporting this international engagement.

Mi-jin Kim:

Who sets the standard sets the future. This is no longer just a slogan; it is reality shaping global competition today.

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Watch the
recording

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